

Information on Data Protection for the PROTEST-AIRT project

Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellowship (Grant Agreement 101057156)

We process your personal data in compliance with the applicable data protection regulations, in particular the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the Brandenburg Data Protection Act (BbgDSG).

The data controller is:

University of Potsdam
Represented by the president, Prof. Oliver Günther, Ph.D.
Am Neuen Palais 10
14469 Potsdam
Phone: +49 331 977-0
Telefax: +49 331-97 21 63
www.uni-potsdam.de

Purpose of the processing

Your data will be processed as part of the research project PROTEST-AIRT that explores the emerging dissent against the global air transport industry. This study includes various data sources such as media texts (newspapers or online reports), interviews, visual materials such as photographs and other innovative techniques. You will be invited to share your political opinions in relation to the right to protest and to the air transport industry, as well as about the potential solutions for the sector in the context of the climate crisis.

Lawfulness of processing

The legal basis for data processing is your consent to the processing of personal data (Art. 6 para. 1 sentence 1 lit. a GDPR). Insofar as political opinions are expressed in the context of the planned interviews, the legal basis for data processing is additionally derived from Art. 9 para. 2 lit. a GDPR (consent to the processing of special categories of personal data).

Withdrawal of consent

You have the right to withdraw your consent at any time and without reason. The withdrawal of consent does not affect the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal.

Duration of data processing

The audio file of your interview will be stored in an external hard drive while being processed, and this external hard drive will be encrypted and kept at a secure location at the University of Potsdam. If necessary, these audio files will be additionally protected with voice distortion during the storage phase. Your file will be transcribed into an anonymized digital text and no personal or sensitive information about you will be included in this file. Each audio file will be labelled with a code and a second protected file will link your name and personal information (age, gender, profession, etc.) to this code. Your audio file will be destroyed immediately after transcription or on June 30th, 2024 at the latest, and any codes linking your name to the audio file will be deleted.

Recipients of your data

Your data will not be transmitted to third parties or other recipients within the University of Potsdam. Excerpts of your anonymized transcription could be used in scientific publications in journals, conferences, public lectures and in communication activities designed for non-academic publics, for example, as part of public education apropos the air transport industry. If you authorized it in the consent form, the anonymized transcription resulting from your interview will be published as open data in a public repository at the end of the research (June 30th, 2024), and it will be accessible to anyone, free of charge. Although the researcher will take all the possible measures to protect you as a participant, it cannot be completely ruled out that re-identification will be possible in the future through a combination with other data sources.

Your rights:

You have the right to obtain from the controller confirmation as to whether or not your personal data is being processed, and, if that is the case, access to the personal data and additional information (right of access). You also have the right to obtain from the controller without undue delay the rectification of inaccurate personal data. If the legal requirements of Art. 17 or 18 GDPR are met, you are entitled to the erasure of your personal data or to a restriction of processing. Please note that restricted processing of the data may not be possible in every instance. You have the right to receive your personal data in a structured, standard, and machine-readable format or to request the transfer to another controller (right to data portability, Art. 20 GDPR). Furthermore, you may object to the processing of your personal data under the conditions set forth in Art. 21 GDPR.

In order to exercise your rights, we kindly request that you contact:

Dr. Alexander Araya López
August-Bebel-Straße 89
14482 Potsdam
Haus 7, Raum 3.30
Phone: [ADD PHONE NUMBER]
E-Mail: [ADD EMAIL]

Access to your personal data can be requested from the Chief Information Officer (University of Potsdam, Karl-Liebknecht-Str. 24-25, 14476 Potsdam). The corresponding form can be found on his website: <https://www.uni-potsdam.de/de/praesidialbereich/praesident-vizepraesidenten/cio.html>.

You can contact the university's Data Protection Officer if you have questions regarding data protection:

[ADD FULL NAME]
Am Neuen Palais 10
14469 Potsdam
Phone: [ADD PHONE NUMBER]
Telefax: [ADD FAX NUMBER]
E-Mail: [ADD EMAIL]

If you think that the processing of your personal data infringes the GDPR, then you have the right to lodge a complaint with the supervisory authority for data protection.